

PAOLA PROJECT

Data Analysis

September 2024

Francisco Valente Gonçalves, PhD
Susana Sousa Lourenço, MSc
Carolina Oliveira Borges, MSc

Funded by
the European Union

PARTNERS

BOCCONI

Bocconi University was established in Milan in 1902 as a private, independent, non-profit university, becoming the first Italian institution of higher education to grant a degree in Economics.

DCU

Dublin City University (<http://www.dcu.ie>) was founded in 1981 and comprises over 17,500 students including over 2600 postgraduate students, of whom c. 800 are research students.

IFA/RUMO

Coordinator
IFA is a non-profit organization that works in the field of mental health and health literacy since 2017.

MCAA

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is an international non-profit organisation created in 2014 with the support of the European Commission, with the aim of increasing the impact of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA).

SciLink

SciLink is an Amsterdam based non-profit foundation, a follow-up training organization of the FP7 MSCA ITN Eduworks-Network, aiming at training researchers across Europe in transversal skills and researcher professionalization.

TI

TI Portugal has focused its attention on becoming a watchdog, trying to follow-up on Portuguese institutions' efforts to improve their integrity practices

SAMPLE

The sample is composed by 117 answers.

Female = 86

Gender fluid = 1

Queer = 1

Male = 28

Missing / NR = 1

Age min = 20

Age max = 55

Age mean = 38

Based in origin country = 77

Not based in origin country = 40

SAMPLE

Nationality

SAMPLE

Place where subject is based

SAMPLE

Degree

SAMPLE

Field of work

Industry or civil so...
5,0%

Government or ot...
10,0%

Academia - resea...
85,0%

ANALYSIS

Have you observed unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

Have you experienced unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

What kind of unethical issues?

ANALYSIS

To what extent do you believe unethical issues are a prevalent problem in academia?

ANALYSIS

How effective are current institutional policies, procedures and tools for prevention?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Lack of Oversight** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Competition** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Hierarchical structure** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Ethical ambiguity** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Publication pressure** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Institutional culture** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Lack of training** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Lack of ethical tools** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Securing funding** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent **Pressure to conform** contribute to the existence of unethical issues in academia?

ANALYSIS

To which extent academic institutions provide **Psychological Support** to individuals?

ANALYSIS

To which extent academic institutions provide **Legal Support** to individuals?

ANALYSIS

To which extent academic institutions provide **Peer Support** to individuals?

ANALYSIS

How transparent are academic institutions in addressing and reporting cases of unethical issues?

ANALYSIS

What are the tools that you are aware of its existence in your institution?

ANALYSIS

What are the tools that you are aware of its existence in your institution?

- Ombudsman
- I was only aware of a designated person in charge of receiving complaints ("provedor"). However, anecdotally as it may be, that person had retired years before and no one was surveilling the dedicated email.
- Equal opportunity commissioner

ANALYSIS

From your knowledge, the ethical tools/strategies in place allow confidentiality?

ANALYSIS

From your knowledge, the ethical tools/strategies in place are easy to navigate?

Yes
12,5%

No
87,5%

Prior conclusions

Unethical issues are recognized as a significant problem.

Current measures for prevention are seen as ineffective.

Transparency in addressing and reporting unethical behavior is low.

Psychological, legal, and peer support from institutions are considered limited.

Issues such as a lack of up-to-date tools, personnel and poor ethical system/tools navigation were reported.

PAOLA PROJECT

Survey data analysis

SEPTEMBER 2024

Funded by
the European Union